

Insper

MULTICLOUD RESOURCE MANAGEMENT WITH COST CONTROLS, KPIS, AND CYBERSECURITY

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Undergraduate Final Project

Capstone Design Report

**São Paulo-SP
December 2023**

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**Capstone Design Report
Report F**

Undergraduate Capstone Design Project Report submitted to the Engineering program (Computer/Mechanical/Mechatronic) in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Bachelor's Degree in Engineering.

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ABSTRACT

This project aims to address the critical challenge of effectively managing expenditures in multicloud environments, where the use of cloud services from different providers is common. Through a partnership between the educational institution Insper and the company PinPag, this endeavor seeks to present a wide-ranging solution capable of monitoring and controlling the services costs, resources and projects across multiple environments, as well as monitoring vulnerabilities, attacks and incidents recorded according to the PCI DSS (*Payment Card Industry Data Security Standard*). The solution will be implemented through a centered dashboard that consolidates all the information about the partner company's infrastructure, allowing for granular visualization of costs, anomalies and outliers. This will be achieved through Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and cloud tools for processing and storing this data. Therefore, the multidimensional approach of this project encompasses both the financial aspect, assisting in keeping expenditures within budget, and the security of related data and systems, ensuring continuous monitoring for potential threats.

Keywords: multicloud, solution architecture, cost management, monitoring, cybersecurity, vulnerabilities, PCI DSS.

1. Introduction

PinPag is a Brazilian company operating in the financial sector as a sub-acquirer, facilitator, and banking correspondent. It intermediates credit and debit card transactions between merchants and acquirers, streamlining digital payments and offering a variety of banking services on behalf of the financial institutions it represents. With a network of over 20,000 retailers and partners, the company processes more than 10,000 transactions daily and operates in all Brazilian states [\[1\]](#).

To support these operations, PinPag leverages a multicloud infrastructure, primarily using AWS (Amazon Web Services) and Microsoft Azure. These cloud providers handle data storage and processing across the various stages of financial transactions, working in tandem based on their designated roles within the system. In this context, AWS is the company's main provider, while Azure was integrated into the infrastructure following the company's acquisition by Linx in 2020. This integration is evident in PinPag's current architecture, where Linx's policies, such as resource tagging, are predominantly applied on Azure.

The adoption of multicloud environments has become the standard for 98% of users of Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) or Platform as a Service (PaaS) [\[2\]](#). This highlights the need for a strategic and unified approach to managing these environments, particularly to address cost challenges. Research conducted by 451 Research and commissioned by Oracle [\[3\]](#), emphasizes this point, revealing that the most common drivers for adopting multiple cloud providers are data sovereignty or location requirements (cited by 41% of respondents) and cost optimization (cited by 40%).

For PinPag, maintaining a well-functioning multicloud environment involves an additional layer of complexity: ensuring the security of sensitive cardholder data. Protecting this information is critical not only for maintaining customer trust but also for meeting industry regulations and standards such as PCI DSS (Payment Card Industry Data Security Standard). Compliance with these requirements is a fundamental aspect of the company's operations. Any failure to meet these standards could result in regulatory penalties, loss of customer trust, or even the inability to process financial transactions – underscoring the importance of robust security measures within PinPag's multicloud ecosystem.

Currently, the company benefits from a monthly service contracted through Linx that provides detailed cost optimization reports, but only for AWS resources. However, no such

service is available for Azure resources. Compounding this issue, as the company undergoes a due diligence process in preparation for acquisition, these AWS reports will soon no longer be available. Additionally, the company utilizes two separate platforms for hardware monitoring and machine security: Zabbix and Wazuh, respectively. A clear limitation of this setup is that, in the event of an attack on a machine, the analysis and decision-making process become fragmented. The procedure requires checking the machine's health status on Zabbix, then reviewing the violated security rules on Wazuh before making an informed decision. This fragmentation between cost and security analyses complicates decision-making and underscores the need for a more unified approach.

Given these challenges, it becomes evident that the company must implement a dedicated dashboard to centralize all information related to cost and security monitoring. A key issue with the current infrastructure is its lack of granular cost analysis, as the testing and production environments are mixed, and no standardized tagging system or distinct signatures exist to separate projects. This lack of organization makes it difficult to monitor and manage resource and project costs effectively.

A primary challenge is presenting and managing costs in a multicloud environment so that expenses generated by each service can be supervised and anomalies quickly identified. Such anomalies might include excessive charges for specific services, costs significantly higher than in previous periods, or expenses that deviate from typical spending patterns. Detecting these irregularities is essential, as they may indicate inefficiencies, operational errors, or potential security issues that require immediate intervention.

In addition to cost management, the company must maintain continuous vulnerability monitoring and conduct regular assessments of common attack types and their severity. Ongoing monitoring is critical for ensuring a secure environment for card payment operations. Rigorous adherence to PCI DSS guidelines and best practices in cybersecurity significantly mitigate the risk of data breaches and financial fraud. This is not only vital for the continuity of PinPag's business but also for maintaining customer trust, ensuring regulatory compliance, and safeguarding its financial operations.

Thus, this project aims to develop the MDI (Multicloud Dashboard Interface), a comprehensive solution for monitoring cybersecurity issues and managing the costs of services, resources, and projects in multicloud environments. The MDI will leverage key performance indicators (KPIs), alerts for cost anomalies and resource usage, and monitoring rules governing

access and traffic to specific services. By creating a dashboard that displays relevant information and metrics – defined in collaboration with the company – in both graphical and numerical formats, the solution will provide a clear and detailed overview of service consumption and machine security across PinPag’s two cloud platforms.

The primary objective is to deliver an efficient and customized tool for the finance department and IT operations team, fostering greater autonomy for the company and improved organization within its cloud environments. This streamlined approach will facilitate the identification of issues, enhance decision-making processes, and improve internal communication. To achieve this, tools and resources from AWS, Azure, Wazuh and Zabbix will be utilized, focusing on capturing data from these platforms, processing it, and integrating it into the dashboard.

1.1 Project Scope

The scope of this project focuses on managing costs and resource usage in multicloud environments, specifically AWS and Azure, with the potential to incorporate additional cloud service providers in the future based on the outcomes of this work. Additionally, the project aims to monitor the security of machines registered on platforms currently used by the company, such as Zabbix and Wazuh, including threat detection and identification of abnormalities within the computational infrastructure.

To achieve these objectives, a centralized dashboard will be developed to provide a unified view of these aspects. KPIs will be defined to facilitate the interpretation of cloud data, enabling cost optimization and improved control over the company’s cybersecurity. These indicators and parameters will be further detailed throughout this document.

It is important to clarify the scope limitations of this project. It does not involve developing a platform for suggesting cost optimizations or resolving existing cybersecurity issues on PinPag’s websites, platforms, or instances. It also excludes the implementation or maintenance of server infrastructure, including tagging servers based on their associated projects. Similarly, the project will not involve external sharing of the dashboard beyond PinPag’s internal use, nor will it implement access controls for Linx members or any other external users. Additionally, the project will not modify the underlying operating systems of

the cloud platforms, perform updates or configurations, or provide support for devices or operating systems outside the predefined scope.

Given the implementation of the solution using AWS and Azure services, it is fundamental to utilize the cost exploration tools provided by these cloud platforms, as well as other essential services, to extract, process, and transmit data to the dashboard. As a result, costs associated with these processes are anticipated. Additionally, there will be restrictions on the KPIs that can be developed, as they will depend on the data made available by the cloud providers. It is also critical to account for the potential costs involved in creating the dashboard itself. The core objective of the project is to integrate information from these environments into the internally developed tool. Consequently, the costs associated with hosting the dashboard must also be considered.

Finally, other optional elements outside the project's scope — but which may be implemented in the future —include conducting a vulnerability analysis of the company's website, primary servers and key machines. Another potential enhancement could involve creating a login system to restrict access to sensitive company information, ensuring that only authorized users can view and manage this data.

1.2 Stakeholder Mapping

Stakeholder	Position	Description
Avner Machado	Network Analyst at PinPag	Direct communication with the PinPag team, assisting in defining the project scope, providing constructive feedback, and helping resolve access issues on the company's platforms. One of the primary users of the interface.
Paulo Kappke	Project Manager at Sonda IT	Another key contact at PinPag, who will assist in understanding the company's resource management needs within its cloud environments. Also, one of the primary users of the interface.

Rodolfo Avelino	Professor at Insper and project supervisor	Serves as a reference for the team, offering expertise, clarifying doubts, and suggesting improvements. Additionally, he will also act as the liaison between the team and the company.
Raul Ikeda	Professor and Coordinator of the Computer Engineering Course at Insper	Assists with administrative matters related to the project, including contract management, business relations, and ensuring the preparation of a scientific document that explains and documents all activities carried out during the project.

1.3 Risk Analysis

During the execution and planning phases of the project, several risks were identified that could impact its success. To mitigate these risks, all identified risks will be outlined here.

Firstly, as mentioned in section [1.1](#), it is important to highlight that the development and implementation of the project involve external costs beyond the platform itself. These costs arise from the need to collect data and establish KPIs, which are critical to achieving the project's primary objectives. Therefore, it is important to remain mindful of the potential risk of exceeding the company's expected budget for the project's execution. While no formal budget has been set, discussions have led to the rejection of certain services due to their high operational costs.

Another significant risk that requires careful attention is the integrity of the company's data and the potential for leaks of confidential information. This risk arises from the fact that, when extracting data from each of the cloud platforms in use, it must be securely stored with the necessary measures in place to ensure its confidentiality and protection.

To address this, a simulation of the real environment and data generation was conducted using an account provided by Insper. However, the generated data and services do not accurately represent the actual data. Simulating the infrastructure of a real environment, particularly regarding digital security, presents challenges as it is always vulnerable to potential failures—technical, digital, or human. Additionally, simulating costs in a controlled

environment often diverges significantly from reality, as unforeseen costs can arise, and many services used by the company are absent from the testing environment. As a result, much of the project was executed directly within the company's infrastructure, requiring even greater caution in handling and processing the data.

Moreover, attention must be given to the tools used for developing the platform, including the dashboard, as well as potential issues such as tool updates, service discontinuations, or changes in how APIs (Application Programming Interfaces) are utilized. These scenarios need to be anticipated, and precautions should be taken to prevent future disruptions related to technology and program functionality.

It is also essential to note that the implementation of certain scalable features requires standardization. For example, the separation of costs by project depends on the use of tags within the company. If the company does not use tags or if they are not standardized, this could lead to errors in the final implementation. It was discussed in meetings with the group and the project advisor that tagging critical or production services should be considered a best practice.

1.4 Ethical and Professional Considerations

This project raises several ethical and professional issues, each of which has significant implications across corporate, economic, and social dimensions. The commitment to confidentiality, integrity, and responsibility is crucial when handling the company's cost and resource data. Access to such data requires a stringent ethical approach to ensure that sensitive information is treated with the highest degree of security, safeguarding it from unauthorized disclosures and leaks.

One key ethical responsibility is the accurate evaluation of the tool's functionality, specifically comparing past costs and verifying their accuracy. This process is vital for ensuring that the results generated by the dashboard are reliable and can serve as a solid foundation for informed decision-making.

To avoid bias and ensure transparency, the project's ethical standards must include clear communication regarding how data is collected, used, and stored, as well as the logic behind the KPIs' formulas. This minimizes the risk of unfair manipulation or distortion of results, thereby maintaining the reliability and impartiality of the information.

From a security and professional perspective, the focus is twofold: protecting the data on the dashboard from potential attacks and securing the data stored on AWS and Azure, the platforms used for processing and storage. Implementing backup strategies and access protocols, such as VPNs, is essential to protect sensitive information from potential threats and breaches. This is fundamental for maintaining a professional and secure approach throughout the project.

Access management and permissions also present a critical ethical concern. Clearly defining who can access and interact with the dashboard is essential to prevent the unnecessary exposure of confidential information. Additionally, incorporating user feedback into the ongoing improvement of the dashboard demonstrates a professional commitment to adapting the platform to meet real needs.

Given the complex ethical and professional implications of this project, the proposed approach is grounded in solid principles of integrity, security, transparency, and responsibility. This ensures that all activities and outcomes are carried out in a lawful and socially responsible manner.

1.5 KPIs

In the corporate world, defining and implementing Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) is critical to the success of projects like PinPag's. These metrics, whether quantitative or qualitative, serve as tools to evaluate the performance of an organization, project, process, or individual in achieving specific goals and objectives over time.

In the context of PinPag's cloud cost management and cybersecurity initiatives, the precise definition of KPIs is particularly significant. These metrics enable the organization to assess its effectiveness in optimizing cloud resources and safeguarding sensitive digital assets. To ensure well-defined and actionable KPIs, the S.M.A.R.T. framework was adopted: Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant, and Time-Bound [\[4\]](#). Each of these principles is outlined below:

Specific: KPIs must be clearly defined, targeting specific aspects of cloud performance and cybersecurity, such as infrastructure costs or threat detection.

Measurable: it must be possible to quantify and measure KPIs, enabling objective analysis. For example, cloud service expenditures can be measured in monetary terms.

Attainable: KPIs should be realistic and achievable within the organization's resources and capabilities.

Relevant: KPIs need to align with PinPag's strategic goals, such as cost optimization and cybersecurity risk mitigation.

Time-Bound: each KPI should have a clear timeframe or deadline to enable progress tracking over time.

Moreover, the primary objective of the dashboard is to offer an intuitive and user-friendly interface, ensuring users can access up-to-date information quickly without requiring a detailed explanatory manual. Therefore, simplicity and clarity in presenting KPIs are essential components of this project.

To identify the most suitable metrics, market benchmarking was conducted [\[5\]](#) [\[6\]](#) [\[7\]](#). This involved analyzing the KPIs employed by similar organizations and selecting those most aligned with PinPag's objectives. This process informed the selection of the cloud and cybersecurity KPIs presented in the following section.

1.5.1 Cloud Service KPIs

The cloud cost metrics have been designed with an appropriate level of granularity to meet the specific needs of the organization. In this context, granularity refers to the degree of detail and precision with which these metrics are generated and analyzed.

Regarding the frequency of generation, these metrics are generated daily, meeting a real need of the organization, providing regular updates of the data. Since cloud costs typically remain stable throughout the day, daily reporting is sufficient for assessing performance and implementing corrective actions when necessary. Adopting a higher frequency, such as hourly updates, would be redundant and unnecessary given the predictable nature of these costs.

Furthermore, the cloud cost metrics are structured to support data analysis over periods of up to three months. This time frame enables the organization to identify trends, seasonal patterns, and cost variations on a quarterly basis. However, the primary focus remains on

month-over-month comparisons, as this approach provides actionable insights while maintaining a balance between granularity and relevance.

With this framework in mind, the KPIs selected for analyzing cloud service costs are outlined below:

KPI	Definition	Benefits
Cloud Cost by Application/Project	This metric quantifies the specific expenditure associated with each application or project running on the cloud infrastructure. It is calculated by summing the individual costs of all cloud resources allocated within a resource group (Azure) or identified by tags (AWS).	Enables precise cost allocation and identifies projects that consume excessive resources, directing cost optimization based on the needs of each application.
Cloud Cost by Service	This metric analyzes the expenditure associated with each specific cloud service (e.g., storage, compute, data processing). It is calculated by summing the costs of all resources tied to a particular service.	Provides insights into which services contribute most to overall costs, highlights opportunities for cost optimization, and informs better resource allocation strategies.
CPU, Memory, and Network Utilization	Assesses the utilization of CPU (Central Processing Unit) resources, memory usage, and network bandwidth by cloud resources. This metric measures the usage rate of these resources over time.	Monitors operational efficiency, identifies usage spikes that could increase costs, and optimizes resource usage based on demand.
Cloud Cost Over a Week	This metric shows the daily cost of all cloud resources over a week. For AWS, this reflects daily costs, while for Azure, it represents cumulative costs up to the current day.	Offers a weekly view of expenditures, enables budget comparisons, and helps detect deviations for financial control and resource optimization.
Mean, Median, and Standard Deviation	This metric calculates the mean, median, and standard deviation of costs over the current month.	Provides a comprehensive view of cost distribution, identifies trends and outliers, and supports monthly expense analysis and optimization.

Resource Usage on Weekends and Weekdays (Monthly)	Analyzes cloud resource usage during different periods of the week, comparing average costs between weekdays and weekends over a month.	Helps identify seasonal usage patterns, optimize resources during peak times, and reduce costs during periods of lower utilization.
Percentage of Tagged Resources	Evaluates the proportion of cloud resources that are tagged with specific information versus untagged resources.	Enhances resource organization and categorization, facilitates identification of owners and purposes, and contributes to overall cost optimization.
Percentage of Service Cost Changes Over the Months	This metric compares the current cumulative expenditure of a cloud service to its total expenditure from the previous month, showing whether costs are increasing or decreasing compared to the same period last month.	Highlights cost trends, enabling timely corrective actions and optimization strategies.
Total Cost Comparison Between the Current and Previous Month	This metric compares the organization's total cloud expenditures for the current month with the previous month. This analysis reveals whether costs are increasing or decreasing from one period to the next, providing insights into cost evolution.	Identifies trends in expenditures, detects significant cost variations, and enables immediate actions for expense optimization and financial control.
Average Cost per Hour of Computing (Monthly)	Calculates the average hourly cost of using cloud computing resources and services over a month. This is obtained by dividing the total expenditure on resources and services by the total usage hours.	Offers valuable insights into the actual cost of cloud computing, allowing for the evaluation of its financial impact. Understanding the average hourly cost of computing supports informed cost optimization decisions and facilitates the selection of more cost-effective computing resources and services.
Cloud Cost by Region (Azure-specific, using more than one region)	Analyzes expenditure based on the geographical region where cloud resources are hosted. Costs are grouped by geographic location.	Identifies regions with the greatest cost impact, supports strategic resource allocation, and helps choose more cost-effective hosting regions.

1.5.2 Security KPIs

Cybersecurity metrics at PinPag differ significantly from cost metrics due to the critical nature of security. Their granularity and frequency are tailored to meet the need for real-time responses to potential threats.

These KPIs are collected and analyzed in real-time, allowing for immediate threat detection and proactive incident responses. Given the dynamic nature of cybersecurity, this approach ensures rapid reactions to safeguard sensitive data and digital assets.

Real-time analysis further enables PinPag to promptly identify and address security events. This continuous, unrestricted monitoring ensures that anomalies are detected and mitigated as swiftly as possible. Such a real-time strategy is vital for maintaining the integrity and security of the organization's digital assets.

The following security KPIs have been implemented:

KPI	Definition	Benefits
Top MITRE ATT&CKs	Developed by the MITRE Corporation, the MITRE ATT&CK framework (Adversarial Tactics, Techniques, and Common Knowledge) categorizes observed actions and behaviors of real-world threat actors. It outlines tactics and techniques to help identify ongoing attacks.	This metric maps alerts generated by Wazuh to specific tactics and techniques, providing the security team with a clearer understanding of the threats affecting monitored servers. This insight enables the development of more effective mitigation strategies.
Incidence of Alerts by Levels	This metric tracks the total number of alerts and categorizes them by severity level.	It helps the security team quickly identify high-severity alerts, allowing for efficient investigation of critical events while maintaining oversight of less severe occurrences.
Evolution of Alerts by Level	Tracks the accumulation of alerts for each severity level over time.	This metric identifies anomalies, such as spikes in specific alert types during certain times of the day or week, providing insights into potential patterns or unusual activity.

Vulnerabilities by Levels	Counts and classifies identified vulnerabilities by severity (e.g., critical, high, medium).	It offers a clear overview of reported vulnerabilities, enabling faster responses to those with higher criticality.
Number of Network Connections per Host	Measures the total number of connections made by each monitored host within a specified time frame.	This assists in identifying and investigating anomalies, such as when numerous connections arise on a given host or when connections occur at times when there should be none.
Source to Destination IP-Port Connections	Maps each established connection by detailing the source IP, destination IP, and the destination port.	This metric provides visibility into network resource usage and allows for the early detection of unusual or suspicious traffic patterns, such as potential intrusion attempts or cyberattacks. It also ensures compliance with security policies.
Highest Alert Level per Host	Identifies the highest alert level detected for each host within a selected time frame.	This allows the security team to prioritize hosts with the most severe alerts, ensuring timely investigation and mitigation.
PCI DSS	The Payment Card Industry Data Security Standard (PCI DSS) establishes security requirements to protect payment card information and ensure secure transactions. This metric identifies which PCI DSS rule applies to specific events recorded by Wazuh.	It helps the cybersecurity team map relevant rules to events, take necessary actions to mitigate potential threats, and maintain PCI certification compliance.

1.6 Review of Related Work

The research in this section focused on identifying and analyzing tools currently used for purposes similar to those of the project. Additionally, a thorough evaluation of each tool's strengths and weaknesses was conducted to determine which best aligns with the company's expectations.

1.6.1 Existing Market Platforms

One of the identified platforms that aligns with the project's objectives is DataDog [\[8\]](#), which integrates with various cloud environments, including AWS, Microsoft Azure, and Google Cloud Platform, among others. In addition to cloud monitoring, DataDog supports database services, Machine Learning, and IoT (Internet of Things). However, it is a paid platform, and each type of monitoring incurs a monthly cost. For example, cloud cost monitoring starts at \$7.50 per host per month [\[9\]](#) and threat monitoring starts at \$10.00 per host per month [\[10\]](#).

Another solution for managing costs and security in an AWS environment is Kion [\[11\]](#). This platform not only provides real-time status updates for each analyzed metric within the infrastructure, but it also includes intelligent features that perform more detailed assessments, propose cost-saving and optimization measures, and offer automation capabilities. These can directly interact with servers, shutting them down based on pre-established conditions to reduce incurred costs. Currently, its cost is \$15,625.00 per unit of use over a 12-month period [\[12\]](#).

A third option that meets the requirements is Densify [\[13\]](#), a company whose product, in addition to traditional real-time monitoring, focuses on workload analysis to provide secure actions for overseeing cloud costs. Its cost ranges from \$39.12 to \$48.30 per instance per year [\[14\]](#).

The companies and platforms mentioned above generally offer similar services. Most focus on cloud cost optimization by conducting analyses and generating accurate reports with suggestions and measures that can be taken to reduce expenses under certain circumstances. Some also strive to automate operations, such as shutting down instances and containers, to stay within a specified budget based on the client's rules. The only platform that offers security monitoring is DataDog, which provides a separate service, while Kion focuses more on cloud compliance¹.

Although all these alternatives are technically valid for the project, they do not fully align with PinPag's expectations. First, hiring third-party providers to monitor cloud environments would require exposing sensitive customer data to external entities, even under

¹ Cloud compliance refers to adherence to industry-specific or organizational regulations, policies, guidelines, and best practices regarding security, privacy, and data regulation in the cloud. It does not necessarily monitor and analyze cloud resources and data in real time to identify vulnerabilities and threats.

confidentiality agreements. The goal is to ensure that no data or information needs to leave the company's own environment. Secondly, the listed services typically come with high costs, which do not align with PinPag's expectations. Since the company has fewer servers and does not deal with large datasets (petabytes), these platforms prove to be somewhat excessive in terms of cost-benefit. Lastly, during company meetings, it has been determined that PinPag prefers to host all its management infrastructure predominantly within its own servers.

Given this scenario, and with the aim of developing a customized monitoring system for PinPag—avoiding unnecessary costs from platforms that the company won't fully utilize—the search for open-source tools integrated into the existing cloud environment within the organization has been chosen.

1.6.2 Existing Solution Architectures

During the research phase, it was observed that many monitoring solution architectures rely on the provider's cloud infrastructure for report generation, data processing, and querying, as mentioned by Mei Lee in her study on cost optimization in cloud services [\[15\]](#). Lee highlights that major cloud providers such as AWS, Azure, and Google Cloud offer integrated cost management tools within their cloud services, enabling the monitoring and optimization of spending on cloud resources. Furthermore, Lee points out that existing multicloud billing monitoring platforms operate through APIs, allowing data collection from various cloud providers, which is then integrated into a unified control panel. This panel provides users with a comprehensive view of current cloud usage, records from different cloud portals, and synthetic monitoring. Therefore, it was decided to utilize native services from the cloud platforms for monitoring and data processing. The specific services used from these cloud platforms will be described in section [1.8](#).

Among the software options considered for building the dashboard, the chosen platform was Grafana. Compared to alternatives such as Tableau, Zoho, and Redash, Grafana proved to be more flexible due to its extensive variety of integration plugins with different cloud providers, databases, monitoring systems, and more. As Patricie Suppala notes in her research on practical FinOps platforms in SaaS and multicloud environments, Grafana is “an open-source tool whose significant advantage is database independence” (SUPPALA, 2022, p.28) [\[16\]](#). This means Grafana does not store the collected data but rather fetches it from the

configured source—an essential feature for handling the diverse data formats across different cloud platforms, monitoring systems, and databases. According to the same research, Grafana is also recognized for its intuitive interface, high-quality graphics, and extensive online documentation.

Based on this research, the team architected and implemented all necessary resources within the respective clouds (AWS and Azure), including the dashboard, which is managed within an EC2 instance on AWS. This solution meets the requirement of keeping the main data flow within the clouds themselves, sending only processed and structured information to Grafana. Furthermore, the project is flexible enough to produce and organize any requested metrics and visualization panels, provided that the necessary data is made available in advance.

1.7 Resources Required for the Project

In addition to the previously available resources – such as the time invested by team members, support from supervising professors, and the time allocated by the organization – several technical and logistical considerations have also been identified. Based on the detailed research presented in the previous section, the necessary resources for the project are outlined below:

1. **Access to platforms and Data:** Considering the project's nature, it is essential to have access to the company's AWS, Azure, Zabbix, and Wazuh accounts. Simulating data access is not feasible due to the following factors: the lack of publicly available examples of cost reports from these cloud platforms; variations in the columns and structure of cost reports depending on the client's specific cloud architecture; the inability to simulate API connections for third-party Wazuh and Zabbix platforms that are not owned by the company. Furthermore, real access is critical to evaluate, test, and implement solutions, ensuring the cost management system operated as intended.
2. **AWS and Azure Tools:**
 - **Cost Analysis Tools:** Since the project focuses on cost management, tools such as AWS Cost and Usage Report and Azure Cost Export are essential.
 - **Data Storage and Processing:** To collect, store, and process data for building KPIs, services like as AWS S3, AWS Glue, AWS Lambda, and AWS Athena

will be used, along with similar Azure services such as Azure Blob Storage, Azure Data Factory, Event Grid, and Azure Data Explorer.

- Integration with Monitoring Platforms: The APIs of Zabbix and Wazuh are fundamental for sending relevant data to the dashboard.
- Backup Tools: To ensure data security for cost reports and processed information, tools like Azure Vault and AWS Backup in AWS will be employed. These tools are critical for implementing robust backup and recovery strategies, such as safeguarding against accidental data deletion in storage locations.

A brief explanation of these tools will follow and will be further elaborated upon in subsequent sections:

Service	Description
AWS S3	Essential for data storage and object availability.
AWS Glue	Key for data preparation and transformation, making data ready for analysis.
AWS Lambda	Serverless service for automatic and scalable code execution in response to events, useful for efficient task automation.
AWS Athena	Allows efficient and interactive queries on data stored in S3.
AWS Backup	A centralized solution for managing backups across AWS services, offering a unified and reliable approach to data protection.
Azure Blob Storage	Offers secure, highly scalable object storage within the Azure platform.
Azure Data Factory	Facilitates the creation, scheduling, and orchestration of data pipelines for ETL

	(Extraction, Transformation, and Loading) processes and integration tasks.
Event Grid + Trigger no Data Factory	Combines Azure Event Grid with triggers in Azure Data Factory to enable automated workflows based on specific events.
Azure Data Explorer	Designed for fast, real-time data analysis, it is ideal for handling high-volume queries and provides advanced querying and visualization capabilities.
Azure Backup Vault	Centralized management for backup operations, ensuring data availability and efficient recovery in the event of failures or data loss on Azure.

3. **Dashboard Tool:** Selecting the appropriate dashboard tool is critical. As previously discussed, the focus was on ensuring data accuracy and effective data handling. For these reasons, Grafana was chosen as the primary visualization platform.

2. Methodology

As previously mentioned, the goal of this project is to develop a dashboard that consolidates all information related to the costs of the cloud environments used by PinPag through KPIs, while also monitoring and displaying important information about the security of these environments. To achieve these objectives and maintain an efficient workflow, the team adopted the agile methodology outlined in the "Manifesto for Agile Software Development" (2001) [\[17\]](#) which emphasizes:

- Valuing individuals and interactions over processes and tools.
- Prioritizing working software over comprehensive documentation.
- Fostering collaboration with the client over contract negotiation.
- Being responsive to change rather than strictly adhering to a predefined plan.

The first principle emphasized the importance of continuous communication and collaboration. The team conducted various meetings and discussions to foster teamwork, extending beyond formal meetings to include constant communication via messages and in-person interactions within Insper's workspaces. Instead of relying on specific project management tools, the team prioritized effective communication, which was deemed sufficient to keep everyone aligned.

While the functionality of the software and the architecture built were given top priority, the significance of documentation was also acknowledged. The aim was to deliver an intuitive and easily comprehensible solution, striking a balance between operational functionality and practical documentation.

The third principle underscored the value of maintaining a close relationship with PinPag stakeholders. Regular follow-up meetings were held with the main contact, Avner Machado, to receive ongoing feedback and refine the dashboard in line with the client's requirements. A messaging channel was also used for real-time updates, ensuring clear and consistent communication about the project's progress. This iterative approach, grounded in direct client feedback, met most expectations while minimizing rework. The frequent and transparent collaboration fostered such a high level of trust that the company granted the team administrative permissions to its cloud platforms, reflecting their confidence in the team's commitment and responsibility.

Finally, throughout the development process, the team encountered numerous challenges and adjustments, demonstrating a readiness to adapt by adding or postponing tasks as needed. This flexibility proved vital for overcoming unforeseen issues and ensuring steady project progress.

Thus, to guide the team's development, the project was divided into weekly sprints. Every Monday, the team met to discuss priorities and distribute tasks efficiently. On Fridays, progress meetings were held with the advisor to share updates, address challenges, and seek guidance when necessary. Furthermore, biweekly meetings were scheduled with PinPag's contacts to align expectations, gather feedback and discuss resource needs. Toward the end of the project, key users such as Avner Machado and Paulo Kappke participated in testing the application to ensure it met expectations.

Finally, to implement this methodology, the following tools were utilized: Notion, WordShare, and WhatsApp. Notion served as a centralized repository, containing all the research utilized during the project's execution, as well as notes from meeting discussions. WordShare served as the collaborative platform for drafting and editing this report. WhatsApp was the primary communication channel for the group, used to provide updates on progress, delegate tasks for each sprint, manage the calendar, and send notifications about important dates.

2.1 Current Infrastructure Overview

During meetings with representatives from the organization, critical insights were obtained about the company's existing infrastructure, which informed the development of the solution architecture. A key observation was that PinPag's current cost monitoring system is integrated with Linx, the company that acquired PinPag in 2020. Furthermore, the company utilizes two cloud platforms: AWS and Azure, with AWS serving as the primary platform.

In AWS, accounts are segregated by project environments. Although a tagging system was not always in place, it has been gradually adopted over the past two years and is expected to become a standard practice in the future. In contrast, Azure does not separate environments by project, such as production or staging, but organizes them primarily by networks. However, as stated during one of the meetings, any resources passing through Linx in Azure are tagged.

Finally, regarding the information to be displayed on the dashboard, it is noted that the granularity for cost events can be set to daily, while security monitoring granularity needs to be continuous. Importantly, the organization expressed a preference for the dashboard not to include recommendations for shutting down machines as a cost-saving measure, as this is not aligned with their operational needs. For instance, the company lacks the flexibility to shut down instances to reduce expenses. Consequently, the dashboard's focus should be on visually presenting both current and historical cloud costs, broken down by services, projects, and other relevant parameters. Additionally, it should provide critical insights into the security status of the company's machines.

2.2 Cost Monitoring Tool Selection

Before detailing the adopted solution architecture, it is essential to outline the rationale behind the selection of cost monitoring tools for the AWS and Azure platforms, which were previously mentioned in the Resources section [\[1.8\]](#).

The AWS Billing and Cost Management service offers a suite of tools to manage bills and optimize costs. Within this service, the Cost and Usage Reports (CUR) provide detailed insights into costs associated with the linked payer account on AWS. These reports include historical cost data stored in an Amazon S3 bucket for subsequent analysis and querying [\[18\]](#). The advantage of CUR over other AWS tools, such as Cost Explorer, lies in its granularity and flexibility. CUR allows data generation at various granularities (hourly, daily, monthly) and in formats such as CSV and Parquet [\[19\]](#). Furthermore, for regular cost analysis, CUR is more cost-effective since Cost Explorer charges \$0.01 per API query [\[20\]](#). Therefore, the decision to generate CUR ensures greater scalability for the project.

In Azure Cost Management, a similar approach was adopted by exporting cost reports stored in a container within a storage account directory. This decision was informed by a consultation with Davi Reis Vieira de Souza, a cloud specialist, during an informal meeting. The consultation revealed that frequent use of the Azure API could result in significant costs, whereas exporting reports provides an efficient way to access and analyze data without repeated API queries.

For AWS, two additional services were selected to process and handle data: AWS Glue and AWS Athena. AWS Glue was chosen for data preparation prior to querying with AWS Athena. Glue manages the data catalog and facilitates the creation, execution, and monitoring of ETL pipelines to load data into data lakes [\[21\]](#). Once processed, data can be queried using AWS Athena, a serverless service that enables the analysis of large datasets with SQL or Python [\[22\]](#). Athena also integrates seamlessly with visualization platforms, including dashboards. To automate these processes, AWS Lambda was chosen, enabling functions to be triggered automatically based on specific events.

An initial consideration was the possibility of transferring data generated in Azure to AWS for processing. However, this approach was ultimately deemed unfeasible for several reasons. Transferring data between cloud platforms would result in significant costs, as such operations are inherently expensive. Moreover, processing the data in AWS would introduce substantial complexity, given the differences in the formats and structures of cost reports from

AWS and Azure. Addressing these discrepancies would require extensive effort to map and convert the data, which would not only slow down the process but also increase the likelihood of errors. Furthermore, this approach would lack scalability in the long term. Any modifications to the cost report formats or expansions of the project scope would entail considerable complications and additional costs.

Considering these challenges, the decision was made to leverage Azure's native tools, such as Azure Data Factory and Azure Data Explorer. These tools, comparable to AWS Glue and AWS Athena, respectively, offer an efficient and scalable environment for processing and analyzing data. By utilizing Azure's native solutions, the project was able to address its requirements effectively while maintaining cost efficiency and ensuring a streamlined, adaptable approach to data management.

2.3 Implementation of the Solution Architecture

Section [1.8](#) outlines the reasons for choosing to create a customized dashboard by PinPag were outlined. decision to develop a customized dashboard. This approach involves manually integrating platforms within Grafana by establishing connections for each data source, centralizing the information into a unified platform. The integration architecture within Grafana is represented in the following diagram:

Figure 1: Diagram illustrating the four data sources that Grafana will consume.

Within each cloud provider, specific tools are employed to construct a pipeline for processing data. Consequently, the operational flow in both AWS and Azure adheres to the following process:

Figure 2: Illustration of the operational flow of the solution architecture to be implemented.

In this process, data is initially retrieved using reporting generation services offered by AWS and Azure. Through an automated workflow, the data is then subjected to a cleaning and transformation stage to produce the necessary KPIs. Finally, the processed data is prepared for querying using SQL or KQL and is seamlessly integrated into the dashboard. The dashboard provides clear and insightful visualizations tailored for effective cost management.

2.3.1 AWS

The project initially focused on exploring and understanding the cost management tools available on cloud platforms. Efforts began with familiarizing and experimenting with AWS tools such as AWS Billing and Cost Management, AWS Lambda, AWS Glue, and AWS Athena. Using AWS credentials provided by Insper, preliminary testing was conducted, which revealed, for instance, that the AWS Cost Explorer APIs were not feasible due to cost considerations, as discussed in section [2.2](#).

Subsequently, using the company's credentials and following AWS's official tutorial and recommendations [\[23\]](#), the following architecture was implemented:

Figure 3: Solution architecture for extracting data from the generated report, processing it, and querying it via the dashboard.

This architecture begins with the generation and storage of a CUR report in an Amazon S3 bucket. Once generated, a crawler is run daily to catalog all data in the report. After the crawler completes, it triggers an AWS Lambda function responsible for initiating data and KPI processing in AWS Glue, resulting in a processed database and corresponding catalog table. Finally, this processed data is queried and referenced using SQL in AWS Athena.

To create the CUR, the AWS Billing and Cost Management section was accessed, specifically the Cost & Usage Reports page. This page allows users to define the report's name, granularity, format, S3 bucket for storage, and integration with AWS tools. The example below illustrates this setup:

Configurar bucket do S3

S3://myBucket

Etapa 3
Analisar e criar

Opções de entrega do relatório

Prefixo do caminho de S3 - obrigatório

Granularidade de tempo dos dados do relatório
Escolha a granularidade de tempo conforme a forma como você deseja que os itens de linha no relatório sejam agregados.

Por hora
 Diariamente
 Mensalmente

Versionamento de relatórios
Escolha se você deseja que cada versão do relatório substitua a versão anterior do relatório ou seja entregue junto com as versões anteriores.

Criação de uma nova versão de relatório
A entrega de novas versões de relatório pode melhorar a audibilidade dos dados de faturamento ao longo do tempo.

Substituição do relatório existente
A substituição de relatórios pode reduzir os custos de armazenamento do Amazon S3.

Integração de dados do relatório

Amazon Athena
 Amazon Redshift
 Amazon QuickSight

Tipo de compactação

Figure 4: Example of basic fields required to create an AWS cost and usage report.

Once configured, the data is generated according to the defined granularity and stored in the specified bucket. For example, data in Parquet format for November 2023 is stored in directories organized by year and month:

Nome	Tipo	Última modificação	Tamanho	Classe de armazenamento
cost-usage-report-00001.snappy.parquet	parquet	3 Nov 2023 03:22:11 AM -03	81.6 KB	Padrão
cost-usage-report-00002.snappy.parquet	parquet	3 Nov 2023 03:22:11 AM -03	375.1 KB	Padrão

Figure 5: Illustration of Parquet data stored in the S3 bucket, sorted by year and month.

For data processing, a crawler was created in AWS Glue to catalog the databases, tables, and schemas present in the raw data stored in S3. A "processed" folder was also added to the same location for storing transformed data [24].

In the crawler creation process, it is necessary to provide information such as the location in Amazon S3 of the data to be cataloged and permission settings in IAM (Identity and Access Management). The image below illustrates the process:

Edit data source [X]

Data source
Choose the source of data to be crawled.
S3

Network connection - optional
Optionally include a Network connection to use with this S3 target. Note that each crawler is limited to one Network connection so any other S3 targets will also use the same connection (or none, if left blank).
[Dropdown] [Refresh]

[Clear selection] [Add new connection]

S3 path
Browse for or enter an existing S3 path.
s3://aws-glue-pinpag-insper/raw-cur/cost-usage-report/cost-usage-report/
All folders and files contained in the S3 path are crawled. For example, type s3://MyBucket/MyFolder/ to crawl all objects in MyFolder within MyBucket.
⚠ This is a required field.

Subsequent crawler runs
This field is a global field that affects all S3 data sources.

- Crawl all sub-folders**
Crawl all folders again with every subsequent crawl.
- Crawl new sub-folders only**
Only Amazon S3 folders that were added since the last crawl will be crawled. If the schemas are compatible, new partitions will be added to existing tables.
- Crawl based on events**
Rely on Amazon S3 events to control what folders to crawl.

Sample only a subset of files
 Exclude files matching pattern

[Cancel] [Update S3 data source]

Figure 6: Example of associating the S3 bucket storing reports during crawler setup.

As part of the setup, a database named "raw-data" was created to store the crawler's cataloged information. The crawler was scheduled for daily automatic execution but can also be run manually:

Crawler properties

Name cur-crawler	IAM role A[...]	Database raw-data	State READY
Description Crawler that will catalog the data generated in the S3 bucket of the cost and usage report.	Security configuration -	Lake Formation configuration -	Table prefix -
Maximum table threshold -			

► Advanced settings

Crawler runs | Schedule | Data sources | Classifiers | Tags

Crawler runs (52)
The list of crawler runs for this crawler.

Filter data | Filter by a date and time range

Start time (UTC)	End time (UTC)	Current/last duration	Status	DPU hours	Table
November 3, 2023 at 12:20:26	November 3, 2023 at 12:21:15	49 s	Completed	0.045	1 tab

Figure 7: Illustration of the AWS Glue crawler, which generates the CUR metadata and stores it in the "raw-data" database.

As a result, the crawler stores all identified schemas in the "raw-data" database. Once configured and operational, the crawler ensures that all generated data becomes accessible for use with other analysis tools. The subsequent step involves utilizing AWS Glue Studio to process the data and apply transformations through a job. During this phase, cost KPIs are constructed using SQL query-based transformations. Notably, each KPI is saved in Amazon S3 within a dedicated directory corresponding to the metric inside the previously established "processed" directory. Simultaneously, the Data Catalog is updated with entries in the "processed-data" database [25]. The job created in Glue Studio is illustrated below:

process-data-insper

Last modified on 09/11/2023, 10:44:12 | Try new UI | Actions | Save | Run

Visual | Script | Job details | Runs | Data quality | Schedules | Version Control

Data source - Data Catalog
all-raw-data

Transform - SQL Query
not-tagged-resources

Transform - SQL Query
changing-cost-per-se...

Data target - S3 bucket
Amazon S3

Data target - S3 bucket
Amazon S3

Data target - S3 bucket
Amazon S3

Data target properties - S3

Format
Parquet

Compression Type
Uncompressed

S3 Target Location
Choose an S3 location in the format s3://bucket/prefix/object/ with a trailing slash (/).
s3://aws-glue-pinpag-insper/process | View | Browse S3

Data Catalog update options | Info
Choose how you want to update the Data Catalog table's schema and partitions. These options will only apply if the Data Catalog table is an S3 backed source.

Do not update the Data Catalog

Create a table in the Data Catalog and on subsequent runs, update the schema and add new partitions

Create a table in the Data Catalog and on subsequent runs, keep existing schema and add new partitions

Database
Choose the database from the AWS Glue Data Catalog.
processed-data

► Use runtime parameters

Table name
Enter a table name for the AWS Glue Data Catalog.
changing-cost-per-service

Figure 8: Construction of the KPIs in the job created in AWS Glue Studio.

When the data is processed using the created job, the results are stored in the target directory specified in Amazon S3. During job execution, its status can be monitored via the "Job Monitoring" interface, as illustrated below:

Figure 9: Page displaying all executed and currently running jobs with their status.

After successful execution, the processed data can be accessed and queried in Amazon Athena:

Figure 10: Example showing access and integration of processed data from AWS Glue with AWS Athena. The left panel indicates that the data source is AWS Catalog, and the selected database corresponds to the processed data.

At this stage, AWS Athena provides access to the cataloged data, allowing for a preliminary visualization of its content:

Concluído Tempo na fila: 193 ms Tempo de execução: 649 ms Dados verificados: 2.8

Resultados (10) Copiar Baixar resultados

Linhas de pesquisa

#	line_item_product_code	date_today	month	year	total_cost	total_usage_hours	avg_cost_per_hour
1	AWSQueueService	2023-10-20	9	2023	1.3415999999999998E-4	391.0	3.431202046035805E-7
2	AmazonInspector	2023-10-25	10	2023	2.354	9.0	0.2615555555555554
3	AmazonInspector	2023-10-25	9	2023	2.354	9.0	0.2615555555555554
4	AmazonEC2	2023-10-31	9	2023	3805.5354490717004	17026.258632775498	0.2235097875082231
5	AmazonInspector	2023-10-31	10	2023	2.3539999999999996	9.0	0.2615555555555554
6	AmazonInspector	2023-10-31	9	2023	2.354	9.0	0.2615555555555554
7	AWSConfig	2023-10-25	9	2023	168.218272	61081.0	0.0027540196133003718

Figure 11: Result of a simple query executed on one of the tables created during AWS Glue processing.

This workflow demonstrates the process of data generation, processing, and querying within AWS. It serves as an example of how the infrastructure was designed to create KPIs and manage cost data, tailored to meet the company's specific needs while focusing on understanding the constructed architecture.

In addition to the KPI processing infrastructure, a backup system for bucket data was established. This backup includes data generated by the CUR (Cost and Usage Report) as well as processed data from the Glue job. The backup configuration was overseen by PinPag stakeholder Avner Machado, leveraging the AWS Backup service as suggested by team members. The backup runs daily to account for new data generation and processing, with a retention period of four months, the minimum allowed by the service. Initially, bucket versioning was considered as a solution, but it only creates new file versions when updates, uploads, or deletions occur, which would not fulfill the goal of maintaining a consolidated daily version of all bucket data. Using another bucket in a different region was also evaluated but dismissed due to the added cost of cross-region data transfer and duplication. Instead, the AWS Backup service, with a cost of \$0.05 per GB per month [26], was chosen. Given the bucket's size of under 100 MB (currently around 23.5 MB), the cost was deemed negligible.

As the reports are cumulative (a Parquet file is generated daily with costs for that day and a summary for the current month), managing the retention period became essential. After discussions with stakeholders, a three-month retention policy was adopted, as the KPIs analyze data up to three months old. Data older than this is unnecessary for analysis, as changes are minimal, and the dashboard aims to provide a current overview of infrastructure costs.

To implement this, a Lambda function runs on the 1st of each month to identify and delete files older than the defined retention period. Below is the code logic:


```

import boto3
from datetime import datetime, timedelta

s3 = boto3.client('s3')

def delete_objects(bucket_name, retention_months):
    current_date = datetime.now()

    # Use o paginador para listar todos os objetos no bucket
    paginator = s3.get_paginator('list_objects_v2')
    result = paginator.paginate(Bucket=bucket_name, PaginationConfig={'PageSize': 1000})

    deleted_objects = []

    for page in result:
        if 'Contents' in page:
            for obj in page['Contents']:
                last_modified = obj['LastModified']
                months_since_last_modified = (current_date - last_modified.replace(tzinfo=None)) // timedelta(days=30)

                print(f'Object: {obj["Key"]}, Last Modified: {last_modified}, Months Since Last Modified: {months_since_last_modified}')

                if months_since_last_modified >= retention_months:
                    try:
                        s3.delete_object(Bucket=bucket_name, Key=obj['Key'])
                        deleted_objects.append(obj['Key'])
                        print(f'Deleted Object: {obj["Key"]}')
                    except Exception as delete_exception:
                        print(f'Error deleting object: {obj["Key"]}, Error: {str(delete_exception)}')

    if deleted_objects:
        print(f'Total objects deleted: {len(deleted_objects)}')
    else:
        print('No objects deleted.')

```

Figure 12: Python code block for the Lambda function that deletes outdated files.

In this context, to verify the retention period, the analysis considered the date of the last modification of the reports. Since the reports are cumulative and updated monthly, the last modification date indicates when the data for that month was finalized and consolidated.

2.3.2 Azure

The analysis began by exploring and leveraging the tools available on Microsoft Azure, including Cost Management + Billing [27], Azure Blob Storage [28], Azure Data Factory [29] e Azure Data Explorer [30]. Credentials provided by Insper facilitated this study, allowing preliminary tests to be conducted. A critical observation during this phase was the economic infeasibility of utilizing Azure Cost Management APIs, as outlined in section 2.2. Based on these findings, the following architecture was designed:

Figure 13: Diagram of the ingestion and processing architecture developed on Microsoft Azure.

At the core of the architecture is the generation and storage of cost reports in a container within Azure Blob Storage. These reports are processed by a pipeline and ingested into Data Explorer, which is responsible for storing and managing the data. Using Data Explorer's query functionality, the processed data is connected to Grafana, where it is visualized through interactive dashboards.

To support this architecture, a storage account was created to manage two distinct containers: one for receiving daily data and another for monthly data, as shown below:

Figure 14: Container page in the storage account created for the application.

The next step involved scheduling report generation [31], setting parameters such as the report name, destination container, and data granularity. The following examples illustrates this process:

New export ...

Exports allow you to create a recurring task that automatically exports your Cost Management data to an Azure Blob Storage on a daily, weekly, or monthly basis. The exported data is in CSV format and contains all the cost and usage information collected by Cost Management. You will incur costs for the Azure storage. [Learn more](#)

Export details

Name *

Metric *

Export type *

Start date (UTC time) *

File Partitioning

Enable partitioning if you have larger datasets and want your exports to be split into multiple files. Please note that if you have partitioning off and it is subsequently turned on, your file schema may change slightly. [Learn more](#)

Off

Storage

Use existing Create new

Subscription *

Storage account *

Container *

Directory *

Figure 15: Illustration of the cost and consumption report scheduling process.

Daily PinPag reports involve exporting data on the company's costs associated with all its services on Azure, formatted in CSV. These reports are generated daily with new entries (rows), detailing the costs of each service from the beginning of the month to the current date. Monthly reports, in contrast, consolidate data on the 5th of each month, summarizing total costs for the previous month.

Using Data Factory Studio [32], two pipelines were developed with accompanying triggers to process and send the data to the Data Explorer database. Pipelines in Data Factory consist of sequential activities, where each step represents a defined responsibility. The completion of one task, depending on its outcome, determines the progression to the next step, critical for the process to advance.

The first pipeline, "ETL-reports," was designed to process incoming data, applying various transformations to generate KPIs. This is achieved using the Data Flow tool, which allows for visual data transformations and processing through blocks.

Figure 16: Illustration of the pipeline creation process in Data Factory.

In the initial activity, there is a process for grouping data and creating new values to facilitate the generation of KPIs, called “Agg_values.” After these transformations, the data is stored in the corresponding tables in the Data Explorer database.

Figure 17: Illustration of the process of creating a Data Flow activity.

Once this task is completed, the main pipeline activity, “KPI_creation,” is initiated to generate and store all KPIs in the database.

Figure 18: Illustration of the KPI creation process.

One challenge encountered concerns the generation of monthly data. The process is scheduled to run only after the 5th of each month, as the consolidated data for the previous month becomes available by then. This scheduling limitation makes it impossible to create the

monthly comparison KPI earlier, causing the pipeline to fail. To address this issue, a feature in Data Flow was utilized, allowing an alternative activity, “KPI_creation_on_fail,” to execute upon failure. During the period from the 1st to the 5th of the month, the monthly comparison KPI is skipped, while other indicators are generated as usual. A potential improvement for the future could involve re-architecting the process to overcome this limitation.

The second pipeline, “monthly-report-transfer,” handles transferring the generated monthly data to the same container where the daily data is stored. This step is crucial due to the way Data Factory triggers operate. When a trigger is activated, pipelines can only access metadata for the specific file that initiated the process. As previous data is inaccessible unless it follows a consistent naming pattern, reports generated with unique identifiers must be renamed to a standardized format for automated reading. To achieve this, the copy activity was selected, enabling file renaming to reflect the current month. Since this activity does not support copying a file to its original location, the file is transferred to the main container instead.

Additionally, a storage event trigger was configured to detect new data in the container and a specific action would be triggered. In the context of this project, this action translates into the execution of the pipeline. The configuration of this trigger is shown in the following image:

The screenshot shows the configuration page for a storage trigger in the Azure portal. The form is set against a dark background. The fields are as follows:

- Name ***: trigger1
- Description**: (empty text area)
- Type ***: BlobEventsTrigger
- Account selection method ***: From Azure subscription, Enter manually
- Azure subscription**: (dropdown menu showing a partially obscured subscription ID)
- Storage account name ***: pfereportstorage
- Container name ***: pfe-container
- Blob path begins with**: pfe-directory/pfe-report
- Blob path ends with**: .csv
- Event ***: Blob created, Blob deleted
- Ignore empty blobs ***: Yes, No
- Annotations**: + New
- Status**: Started, Stopped

Figure 19: Creation of storage triggers.

Therefore, for each report generated and stored in the container, the trigger is activated and executes the pipeline. Upon completion, the pipeline ingests the processed data into Data Explorer [\[32\]](#).

Figure 20: Tasks responsible for sending data to Data Explorer.

Azure Data Explorer, a robust and fast data analytics service offered by Microsoft Azure, plays a key role in managing large volumes of structured, semi-structured, or unstructured data. In this project, it acts as a crucial link between the processed data and the Grafana platform. Its operation involves setting up a custom cluster in the PinPag environment, equipped with an execution engine for queries using the KQL language and an integrated database. This cluster manages data ingestion, table creation, and schema definition to meet specific requirements.

The screenshot shows a database interface with a sidebar on the left listing tables under the 'kusto_db' database. The tables listed are: costByProduct, costByProject, costByRegion, costByService, costPerHour, costRatebyService, dailyCost, monthComparison, notTaggedPercent, statsDescription, totalDailyCost, and weekdayWeekendAvg. On the right, a table preview is shown with columns: ProductName, total_c..., and Date. The preview shows 12 rows of data, all dated 2023-11-08, with ProductName values starting with S, V, P, S, V, B, S, V, V, B, and A.

ProductName	total_c...	Date
> S		2023-11-08
> V		2023-11-08
> P		2023-11-08
> S		2023-11-08
> V		2023-11-08
> B		2023-11-08
> S		2023-11-08
> V		2023-11-08
> V		2023-11-08
> B		2023-11-08
> A		2023-11-08

Figure 21: Preparation of the database that consumes the data and eventually sends it to Grafana.

Finally, rules were also implemented for cleaning tables, deleting unused files, and managing backups. It is important to highlight the existence of two types of storage in the Azure architecture: the container and the Data Explorer database. Unlike AWS, which allows direct querying in the bucket using Data Catalog metadata, Data Explorer's requires both storage types due to its limitations in this regard. Database cleanup begins with the monthly activation of the "monthly-report-transfer" pipeline, which now also removes KPI rows from previous months. This step prevents unnecessary accumulation of outdated data. Upon completing the copy activity, several parallel queries are executed in Data Explorer to delete obsolete rows, ensuring only relevant and up-to-date information is retained.

Figure 22: Parallel activities responsible for cleaning the tables.

Regarding file deletion management from the container, a lifecycle management policy was implemented. Under Life Cycle Management, a rule was established whereby all files created over 90 days ago are automatically deleted. This policy ensures the elimination of obsolete data and prevents unnecessary accumulation, focusing on recent files containing accumulated and updated information.

Figure 22: Validity and deletion rules.

As for the backup strategy, a rule was defined in the Data Protection section of the container. This required the creation of an Azure Backup Vault—a centralized repository for storing backups—and the configuration of a policy. Daily backups are performed with a retention period of seven days, similar to AWS, ensuring data protection without excessive accumulation.

2.3.3 Zabbix

To monitor instances across all cloud infrastructures, several tools are available, including services like AWS CloudWatch, which tracks daily metrics such as CPU usage, memory consumption, and network traffic for each platform instance. However, in pursuit of standardizing a unified hardware analysis method that works across multiple cloud environments, one of the most widely used and effective tools is Zabbix [\[33\]](#). Zabbix is an open-source monitoring system designed to oversee and manage IT infrastructures, networks, and services in real-time. It provides comprehensive monitoring of key performance metrics such as CPU and memory usage, network traffic, and application-specific data.

The platform functions by deploying agents on the devices to be monitored, enabling continuous data collection. These agents provide detailed insights into resource utilization, such as CPU and memory usage, as well as metrics tailored to specific applications. This flexible and extensible design makes Zabbix a highly adaptable solution for managing environments of all sizes, from small-scale infrastructures to complex, large-scale implementations. The collected metrics can be easily accessed and visualized through the Zabbix dashboard, as illustrated in the image below:

Figure 23: Screenshot of the PinPag Zabbix homepage, demonstrating on the left side where to access the hosts and their metrics.

By selecting the "hosts" option on the left side of the dashboard, users can view a list of all machines where the Zabbix agent is installed. This allows for quick access to a variety of metrics, as demonstrated below:

Figure 24: Screenshot of the Zabbix page displaying all available hosts from PinPag.

Figure 25: Screenshot of the Atendedor-AWS host, showcasing disk usage charts as an example

In the above images, the process of accessing the Atendedor-AWS host among all available hosts in the company's Zabbix system is displayed. Here, various metrics, such as disk usage, can be reviewed in detail.

Additionally, Zabbix provides advanced alerting and notification capabilities, enabling proactive identification of potential issues before they impact critical services. Alerts can be customized based on specific performance parameters or critical events, ensuring timely responses to disruptions and minimizing downtime.

In summary, Zabbix offers comprehensive real-time monitoring while excelling in flexibility, scalability, and robustness. Its proactive detection and resolution capabilities make it a strategic choice for organizations aiming to standardize and optimize hardware analysis across cloud environments. This, in turn, promotes operational efficiency and service reliability.

All necessary credentials for accessing and using the Zabbix platform were provided by PinPag, allowing for the verification of data displayed on the dashboard against the actual metrics reported by the service. This also ensured seamless connectivity with both the dashboard and the platform.

2.3.4 Wazuh

Monitoring and analyzing vulnerabilities or potential attacks on infrastructure can be achieved using various platforms, with Wazuh standing out as an especially notable option. Wazuh is an open-source platform widely recognized for its effectiveness in monitoring and managing IT infrastructures, networks, and services in real-time. It offers configurable alarms and alerts to address critical vulnerabilities.

Similar to Zabbix, Wazuh requires the installation and configuration of agents on all environments and machines to be monitored. These agents generate a wealth of data and metrics, which can be visualized as shown in the following images:

Figure 26: Screenshot of the PinPag Wazuh homepage, illustrating the visualization options available.

Figure 27: Screenshot of Wazuh's active hosts page, displaying events for each host individually.

Figure 28: Screenshot of the Atendedor-AWS machine agent and its corresponding security events detected by Wazuh.

The images above highlight various features of the Wazuh platform, such as security event detection, integrity monitoring, general vulnerabilities, MITRE ATT&CK analysis, and more. By selecting "active hosts," a list of all machines monitored by Wazuh is displayed. Clicking on a specific host—such as the Atendedor-AWS—reveals a detailed list of security events associated with that machine.

Wazuh plays a critical role in ensuring the integrity and security of IT infrastructures, offering a robust and efficient solution for monitoring vulnerabilities and detecting potential attacks. Its comprehensive approach to threat management facilitates the rapid identification and mitigation of security breaches.

A key strength of Wazuh is its ability to collect and analyze log data from various devices and applications, presenting a structured overview of the infrastructure's security posture. The platform excels at correlating seemingly unrelated events to identify patterns and suspicious activity, enhancing the accuracy of threat detection and enabling proactive responses to emerging risks.

Wazuh also supports the configuration of alarms and alerts for severe threats, allowing for immediate responses to incidents. This functionality helps prevent malicious exploits from compromising infrastructure security by enabling the implementation of corrective measures in a timely manner.

Similar to the use of Zabbix for hardware monitoring across all cloud infrastructures, Wazuh is employed as a unified platform for analyzing and monitoring vulnerabilities and potential attacks on PinPag's IT infrastructure.

All necessary credentials for accessing and utilizing the Wazuh platform were also provided by PinPag, ensuring seamless connection to the configured dashboard and enabling thorough monitoring of the system.

2.3.5 Grafana: Dashboard Creation and Platform Integration

Grafana [34] plays a pivotal role in the visualization and analysis of collected data, enabling the creation of graphs, tables, histograms, and heat maps as required. These dashboards provide a clear and explicit visual representation of costs and performance metrics, which are updated regularly, whether every minute or daily. Each data point is gathered through the platform, which integrates with AWS and Azure cloud infrastructures using the necessary credentials.

The development of an initial prototype dashboard and testing with these platforms required several steps [35]. First, users must create a free account on the Grafana platform and set up a project.

Upon logging in, Grafana provides two primary methods for managing dashboard installation and configuration [36]. The first option is to operate directly through the cloud platform, while the second involves installing the Grafana agent locally, which allows hosting on a local machine or a web server. Additionally, there is a third option: using Grafana through an AWS account, referred to as Amazon Managed Grafana (AMG) [37]. However, AMG presents significant drawbacks, such as potential integration issues with Azure when the dashboard is intrinsically linked to an AWS account. There are also concerns about data integrity and availability, as the platform may be vulnerable to attacks that could compromise data and lead to significant losses. These risks can be mitigated by ensuring that Grafana independently manages data security and access, decoupling it from AWS accounts.

For these reasons, the project initially opted to use Grafana directly via its website, leveraging Grafana Cloud (a cloud platform also utilized by AWS), to enhance the security, scalability, and availability of the dashboard. This approach enables the use of authentication tools, such as SAML and others shown in the figure below:

Advanced Auth

Configuring stack pfepinpag

Grafana instances support OAuth, SAML, and LDAP. For OAuth, select your provider below. If your provider is not listed here [open a support ticket](#). To [configure SAML](#) visit your Grafana instance.

Figure 29: Screenshot of the "Advanced Auth" screen in Grafana, indicating the available authentication methods.

After creating the account and project in Grafana, users are redirected to the following page:

Figure 30: Screenshot of Grafana displaying the options available to users when creating a project.

As noted earlier, Grafana Cloud was used in this setup. By selecting "Launch" in the Grafana selection box, as shown in the figure above, all necessary resources are provisioned in the cloud, leading to the following page:

Figure 31: Screenshot of the Grafana Cloud startup page after launching.

This page provides various details to the user, with the most notable being the number of users and metrics. The "active users" section shows how many users are currently allocated and using the platform, categorized as Editors or Viewers. Below that, the "Limit" section outlines the maximum number of users allowed under the current plan. Similarly, the "metrics" section displays the number of metrics extracted and utilized in the dashboard, capped at 10,000 for the free plan.

At this stage, the next step is to connect Grafana to the necessary platforms, infrastructures, or data sources for monitoring. Establishing these connections provides the foundation for creating visualization templates. Below are examples of possible connections available for use with Grafana:

Figure 32: Screenshot showcasing possible connections with Grafana.

Among the various available options, the project utilized the following data sources for the prototype:

Figure 33: Screenshot showing services used for the first dashboard prototype.

Figure 34: Additional screenshot of services used for the first dashboard prototype.

The data sources utilized for the project, as shown in the images above, included Amazon Athena, CloudWatch, and Azure Data Explorer. These sources enabled seamless connections to their respective cloud platforms, facilitating data extraction and visualization within the dashboard. Initially, Grafana Cloud was used to establish these connections, a process that will be detailed later. Importantly, the steps for establishing these connections remained unchanged even after adjustments to how Grafana was deployed. The reasons for this change will also be clarified further in this section.

To connect to AWS CloudWatch [38], users must select the "CloudWatch" option, as shown in the image above. Upon selection, the following configuration page appears:

Figure 35: Screenshot of CloudWatch connection configuration in Grafana.

After adding CloudWatch as a data source in the user's Grafana account, the connection becomes available for future queries, alongside various example dashboards. This enables users to fetch data that can be displayed in panels.

The connection process for CloudWatch is outlined below:

Figure 36: Illustration of the connection between Grafana and AWS CloudWatch.

On this configuration screen, users only need to provide the access key and secret key associated with the AWS account being monitored. It is recommended to create a dedicated user with restricted permissions for monitoring purposes. This approach was implemented during initial testing with Insper's AWS account and later adopted by PinPag.

Once the keys are entered, the connection can be tested. If successful, all CloudWatch data from the provided AWS account becomes accessible. This data allows real-time monitoring of services, running instances, and their resource consumption (e.g., memory, internet traffic, and CPU usage).

After successfully establishing the connection, users can proceed to create a dashboard. By navigating back to the homepage (refer to [Figure 20](#)) and selecting "Dashboards," users are redirected to the following screen:

Figure 37: Screenshot of the dashboards tab within Grafana, showing all existing dashboards in the user's account.

When creating a dashboard, the following page is displayed:

Figure 38: Screenshot of creating a new dashboard in Grafana.

To enable data visualization and analysis, a new panel must be added to the dashboard:

Figure 39: Screenshot of adding a new panel to the dashboard with CloudWatch as the data source.

By selecting CloudWatch in "Data Source," various queries can be performed according to the analysis parameter selected that is available through the connection with the service:

Figure 40: Screenshot showing data captured from AWS EC2 through the CloudWatch connection.

In the example above, the AWS EC2 service was selected, with the average CPU usage of running instances as the measured parameter. Each instance ID displayed in the chart legend corresponds to an EC2 instance, with its average CPU consumption percentage tracked over a 30-day period.

Building on this example, several additional metrics, data sources, and infrastructures were connected to Grafana, culminating in the initial prototype dashboard shown below:

Figure 41: Screenshot of the dashboard after connecting various metrics using Insper's test account.

The image above highlights key metrics such as monthly and daily costs across AWS services and platforms.

However, connecting to the Zabbix platform (previously discussed in section 2.2.3), required additional steps. Unlike CloudWatch, Grafana does not include a pre-installed plugin for Zabbix, so users must manually install it. The plugin installation process is initiated via the following page [39]:

Figure 42: Screenshot of the Grafana plugin installation page.

After searching for "Zabbix" on this page, the plugin can be identified and installed [40]:

Figure 43: Screenshot of the Zabbix plugin installation page.

Once installed, the Zabbix plugin appears as an option in the data sources tab (see [Figures 33 e 34](#)). When adding Zabbix as a data source [\[41\]](#), users are presented with the following configuration screen:

Figure 44: Screenshot of the Zabbix data source configuration page.

To establish the connection, the URL for the Zabbix service must be provided, appending "api_jsonrpc.php" to the host address. In PinPag's case, the initial credentials provided were insufficient, and several metrics (e.g., CPU and memory usage) had been missing since June 28, 2023. After identifying this issue, new credentials were issued, and the necessary Zabbix agents were reinstalled by PinPag, resolving the problem.

Once the updated connection was established, a new dashboard prototype was created to visualize the data, as shown below:

Figure 45: Screenshot of the dashboard prototypes with Zabbix connections.

Figure 46: Screenshots of the dashboard prototypes with Zabbix connections.

These dashboards display CPU usage metrics for both Windows and Linux instances on AWS. Similar visualizations were used to monitor memory usage across AWS instances and Azure virtual machines.

For the Wazuh integration, additional adjustments were necessary. Grafana uses the ElasticSearch plugin to communicate with Wazuh, which operates on port 9200. However, due to PinPag's security policies, this port was blocked on the Wazuh host machine. To address this, changes were made to how Grafana was hosted.

As previously mentioned, Grafana provides three hosting methods for dashboards and related services. One such method involves a local installation of Grafana, which operates on port 3000 of localhost. In the initial attempt to address the issue, an instance was created in AWS by Insper to perform preliminary project tests. A reverse proxy was then configured on this instance, enabling Grafana to connect to the Wazuh service running on port 9200 of PinPag's machine by accessing the instance's IP on the same port. To ensure connectivity, PinPag was requested to grant access to port 9200 exclusively for the IP of the AWS instance created by Insper.

Despite the reverse proxy functioning correctly in this initial setup, Grafana was unable to process the configuration, making it impossible to access Wazuh in this manner. Consequently, the decision was made to create an instance directly within PinPag's AWS infrastructure. Grafana was installed and configured locally on this machine, and its IP address was authorized in the security group of the Wazuh machine. This approach provided more control over logs, databases, errors, access, and overall dashboard security. Additionally, a dedicated VPN was established for group members and PinPag to securely access the dashboard. This measure restricted access to external parties, mitigating potential data breaches and ensuring information security.

After completing these steps and successfully implementing the changes, a .pem file was distributed to each group member. Using the OpenVPN service, this file was imported to enable the VPN connection, allowing access to the dashboard between 9:00 AM and 9:00 PM:

Figure 47: Screenshot showing the VPN connection to PinPag, allowing access to the dashboard.

Once the connection was established, users could access the IP address of the Grafana-hosting machine via port 3000 in a browser. Upon doing so, the login page prompted for a username and password. In the example below, the administrator account created by the project team members was used:

Figure 48: Screenshot of the Grafana login screen located on the PinPag instance.

After logging in, the connection between Wazuh and Elasticsearch could be established:

Figure 49: Screenshot of the ElasticSearch connection screen in Grafana.

he necessary options and details to establish the connection are highlighted, including the Wazuh service URL (port 9200) and the access credentials provided by PinPag. For the Wazuh dashboard, the visualizations were based on a [\[42\]](#) template freely provided by Recife Tecnologia on their LinkedIn page:

Figure 50: Wazuh dashboard template on Grafana provided by Recife Tecnologia.

The template includes a panel displaying the total number of vulnerabilities identified on hosts, categorized by risk level, alongside visualizations of event distributions by alert severity, key MITRE ATT&CK tactics, geolocated monitoring points, and network activity maps. Pie charts categorizing events by various parameters were used to implement the KPIs “Top MITRE ATT&CKs” and “Alert Incidence by Levels.” Other visualizations could not be utilized due to limitations in Wazuh’s configurations, which prevented capturing the necessary data. Adding new metrics to address these gaps would have required restarting the Wazuh agents’ hosting machines, which was not possible during the company’s audit. Consequently, KPIs like “Vulnerabilities by Levels,” “Number of Network Connections per Host,” and “IP-Port Connections from Source to Destination” were not implemented.

To enhance the Wazuh dashboard, a graph was added to identify monitored hosts and their respective internal IPs. For any monitored machine, its name and IP address automatically appear in a side table, provided an event for that server exists within the selected time range. The following visualizations were created for the Wazuh security panel:

Figure 51: Overview panel of the Wazuh dashboard.

Figure 52: Overview panel of the Wazuh dashboard with PCI compliance visualizations.

In the above figures, a graph displaying the highest alert levels detected on hosts fulfills the “Highest Alert Level per Host” KPI. The “Overview” section also includes PCI compliance visualizations, such as the most frequently detected PCI rules and a table detailing agents and

their associated occurrences. The final graph in this section tracks the “Evolution of Alerts by Level” KPI.

Separate panels were added for each server to display the distribution of alerts. However, due to limitations in the connection tool between Grafana and Wazuh, these panels cannot dynamically update when new monitoring points are added. Each point must be added manually.

Figure 53: Visualization panels for individual hosts.

For the cost dashboard, hosted in PinPag’s cloud environment, connecting to AWS Athena, which houses most AWS cost KPIs, followed a process similar to that of CloudWatch. The data source was added by providing access and secret keys for the AWS account. Visualizations were then created by selecting the desired database and table and constructing the corresponding SQL query. Below is an example query:

```

1 WITH today AS (
2   SELECT
3     DATE_FORMAT(CAST("data_inicio" as timestamp), '%d/%m/%Y') AS "Data",
4     "total_cost" AS "Custo total"
5   FROM
6     "cost-per-week"
7   WHERE
8     "date_today" = CURRENT_DATE
9 ), yesterday AS (
10  SELECT
11    DATE_FORMAT(CAST("data_inicio" as timestamp), '%d/%m/%Y') AS "Data",
12    "total_cost" AS "Custo total"
13  FROM
14    "cost-per-week"
15  WHERE
16    "date_today" = CURRENT_DATE - 1
17 )

```

Figure 54: Example of an SQL query calculating daily costs over a week in AWS.

In this query, a temporary table called “today” is created, along with another table named “yesterday” (not shown in the image). This setup is used to check whether data marked with today’s date exists, indicating that the AWS Glue job has already been executed and the KPIs for today have been generated. If such data exists, the visualization displays today’s processed data. Otherwise, it defaults to show yesterday’s data. This logic was applied across all visualizations built into the dashboard with AWS information. Below is an example of the corresponding visualization for the demonstrated query:

Figure 55: Visualization of the query that calculates daily AWS costs over a week.

Similarly, to connect to Azure Data Explorer, which stores all Azure cost KPIs, it was necessary to first add the data source. Once configured, visualizations in the Azure dashboard could be created by selecting the desired database and table. However, the queries in this case were built using KQL (Kusto Query Language), which is specifically designed for exploring, analyzing, and visualizing data in Azure Data Explorer. An example query is shown below:


```

1 let today = todatetime(now());
2 let sixDaysAgo = todatetime(now() - 6d);
3 totalDailyCost
4 | extend DaysDifference = datetime_diff('day', Date, sixDaysAgo)
5 | where DaysDifference >= 0 and DaysDifference <= 6
6 | project Date, total_cost
7

```

Figure 56: Query that shows the daily cumulative cost over a 7-day period.

This query selects the total accumulated cost up to a specific day for records from the last seven days, calculated by checking the difference in days between the record's date and the date six days prior. The resulting visualization is shown below:

Figure 57: Visualization of the query showing total cost evolution over a week.

For most of the other KPIs, the same logic used in the AWS queries was adopted in Azure. This involved verifying whether data marked with today's date exists, indicating that the pipeline in Azure had been executed and today's KPIs had been generated. If not, yesterday's data is displayed instead.

A noteworthy limitation arose with one of the Azure KPIs. While AWS allows for analyzing hourly service costs over a three-month period, this approach was not feasible on Azure. Azure Data Factory operates using metadata provided by the trigger when a cost report file is added to the container. The pipeline only runs when the trigger is activated, which occurs when new data is added to the container. Consequently, Data Factory manipulates metadata from the trigger, making it impossible to retrieve files for previous periods. Although storing

this data in an alternative location, such as Azure SQL Database, was considered, it was ultimately rejected by the stakeholder due to additional costs. Despite this limitation, the analysis remains focused on the most current and updated information, ensuring accuracy and relevance. This approach aligns with the project's objectives, even within the constraints of Azure's pipeline setup.

Another key aspect of the dashboard's design was its division into four distinct panels: one for AWS cost and consumption information, another for Azure, one for infrastructure health monitoring via Zabbix, and one for event monitoring through Wazuh. The decision to separate the panels by cloud provider and specific functionalities was based on the organizational structure of the company's environments.

As previously mentioned, Azure began being used by PinPag after its acquisition by Linx, which means much of the Azure infrastructure is more closely tied to Linx than to PinPag. This distinction is reflected in the different activities conducted in each cloud, which leads to a significant variation in the costs generated by each platform. Consequently, analyzing both clouds together would not yield meaningful insights, given their operational differences. Additionally, Zabbix and Wazuh serve distinct purposes within the monitoring spectrum. Separating these resources into individual panels was a deliberate choice to maintain clarity and avoid overcrowding the visualizations. Despite this separation, the overarching goal of unifying all relevant information into one dashboard was achieved, enabling a comprehensive understanding of the metrics.

Finally, it is worth noting the differentiation between the cost and security panels, which was based on the distinct user profiles who utilize them. The security panels are intended for users like Avner Machado, who are familiar with the field and require less explanatory detail in the visual metrics. On the other hand, the cost panels cater to two different profiles: the developer, Avner Machado, and Paulo Kappke, who has deeper expertise in financial management.

To address this, the cost panels were designed with more detailed descriptions of the metrics, accommodating the varying knowledge levels and needs of the users. Concise and self-explanatory titles were prioritized to enable instant understanding of the presented metrics. This strategy ensures a more personalized and effective data visualization experience for users with different requirements.

By tailoring the panels to the specific demands of each user profile, the interface facilitates data interpretation and use in a manner that is both assertive and aligned with individual expectations.

2.4 Proposed Architecture Costs

The cost estimation for the infrastructure was conducted separately for each cloud provider, considering scenarios that assume excessive resource usage—beyond what is actually planned. This approach aimed to propose a model to the client with a built-in safety margin for costs, ensuring that the actual expenses are expected to be lower than those outlined in the following paragraphs.

2.4.1 Grafana

The first component evaluated in the cost analysis was the hosting of the Grafana application. During approximately the first half of the project's development, the decision was made to use Grafana's online platform, which offers free resources that initially met the needs of both the team and the company. The free version [\[43\]](#) includes:

- Up to 3 active monthly users.
- Up to 10,000 metrics to be monitored.
- Up to 50 GB of data traffic.

Since the reports generated by the cloud platforms and monitoring services are measured in kilobytes (kB), and the company does not have an infrastructure large or complex enough to generate several megabytes (MB) of data daily, it was estimated that the 50 GB traffic limit would be sufficient to support PinPag's operational activities without requiring an upgrade. Additionally, as only one individual would be responsible for managing the application, the free plan was deemed adequate. If the number of active users needed to exceed three, an option would be to upgrade to the next plan, which costs \$29.00 per month.

However, during the project, limitations emerged in building the dashboard ([section 2.3.5](#) related to Wazuh). Following alignment meetings with stakeholders, a request was made to run Grafana directly within the company's environment using an EC2 instance on AWS. This decision allowed PinPag to maintain full control over the number of users and data traffic, with the associated cost being limited to the computational unit dedicated to hosting Grafana. Consequently, no direct costs were tied to the application itself, only to its hosting on the EC2 instance.

2.4.2 AWS

The first resources analyzed in AWS, using the AWS Pricing Calculator [44] were those suitable for hosting the Grafana application. The initial option considered was AWS Fargate, a service that runs containers. In this case, the group would be responsible for creating and configuring a container to run on the platform. Since Fargate pricing is based on computational resources (RAM and number of vCPUs) and daily usage hours, several factors were considered before making cost calculations:

1. The software requires a minimum of 4GB of RAM and 1 vCPU.
2. Application usage might be sporadic (e.g., 2 hours per day).
3. Usage could also be intensive, particularly for monitoring security metrics (24 hours a day).

Based on these scenarios, two configurations were analyzed: a container with 2 vCPUs and 8 GB of RAM to accommodate higher memory demand for integrated monitoring resources; a container with 2 vCPUs and 4 GB of RAM for a more standard workload. The cost estimates for these configurations are summarized in the tables below:

Table 1 – Cost estimation for a container with 2 vCPUs and 8 GB RAM.

Usage (hours/day)	Monthly Cost (US\$)
1	3,68
2	7,36
24	88,31

Table 2 - Cost estimation for a container with 2 vCPUs and 4 GB RAM.

Usage (hours/day)	Monthly Cost (US\$)
1	1,91
2	3,81
24	45,77

The second candidate was AWS EC2 (Elastic Compute Cloud), which offers virtual machines running various operating systems, fully customizable based on user requirements. EC2 instances can operate 24 hours a day or be temporarily shut down. The configurations analyzed matched those of the Fargate option.

Table 3 – Cost estimation for EC2 Instances.

Instance Type	vCPUs	GBs RAM	Monthly Cost (US\$)
t2.medium	2	4	36,43
t2.large	2	8	70,30

While EC2 instances offer a cost advantage for continuous use, they are less economical for sporadic usage. Additionally, they require more operational effort to configure the operating system and implement cybersecurity measures to ensure functionality and protection against vulnerabilities.

As discussed in the previous section, an EC2 instance was eventually chosen to host Grafana, and the monthly cost for this virtual machine was included in the final project budget.

Next, Amazon Athena was analyzed. Athena is a serverless, interactive query service that enables SQL-based analysis of data stored in Amazon S3. Built on Presto, a distributed open-source query engine, Athena eliminates the need to set up and manage data processing clusters, which are often expensive and complex. Athena's pricing is based either solely on SQL queries or on the use of additional computational services, such as provisioning processing capacity or leveraging Apache Spark. For this project, dedicated computational resources were unnecessary, so cost estimation focused exclusively on the number of queries executed daily and the amount of data processed. Assuming a rate of 1,000 queries per day, with each query processing 10 MB of data, the estimated monthly cost was \$1.45.

AWS Glue, a fully managed ETL service by AWS, plays a vital role in preparing data for analysis within cloud storage and processing environments. Its architecture includes components such as the crawler, which automatically catalogs metadata from data sources, and the Data Catalog, which stores essential information about schemas and transformations. As mentioned earlier, AWS Glue offers automation, scalability, and security features, making it an effective choice for organizations seeking to streamline and accelerate the data preparation process. This results in greater agility in extracting valuable insights from their data resources in the AWS cloud.

AWS Glue pricing is determined by the use of various tools available within the service. For this project, only specific tools were utilized, and their costs were calculated as follows:

- ETL jobs and interactive sessions: Costs are based on the number of DPUs (Distributed Processing Units) used for Apache Spark and the duration of job execution. For this

project, 2 DPUs (the minimum offered by AWS) and 300 minutes per month (approximately 10 minutes per day) were estimated, resulting in a cost of \$4.40.

- AWS Glue Data Catalog Storage Requests: Costs are determined by the number of stored objects and access requests. Assuming 1,000 objects and 1,000 requests per month (an overestimate for this project), the cost was \$0.01.
- AWS Glue Crawlers: Costs are calculated based on the number of crawlers and their runtime. It was estimated that 0.25 DPUs (equivalent to 1 vCPU and 4 GB RAM) would be needed for 5 hours of monthly crawler activity, costing \$0.55.

Thus, the total monthly cost for AWS Glue was estimated at \$4.96.

AWS Lambda is a serverless computing service that allows developers to execute code without managing servers. Lambda is particularly useful for promoting agility, scalability, and efficiency in cloud-based application development. Its pricing is based on the number of invocations, execution duration, allocated memory, and storage. For this project, the following usage was estimated:

- 10,000 requests per month.
- 2 minutes of execution per request.
- 1 GB of RAM.
- 2 GB of temporary storage.

The total monthly cost for AWS Lambda was calculated at \$13.39.

Finally, Amazon S3 (Simple Storage Service) was selected as the cloud storage solution. S3 is highly scalable and durable, designed to store and retrieve large volumes of data efficiently and securely. Using an object storage architecture, data is stored in buckets and accessed via unique URLs. S3 is widely used for various purposes, including website hosting, data backup, content distribution, and big data analytics, due to its high availability, durability, and scalability.

The cost estimation for Amazon S3 included the following:

- Storage: 50 GB per month using S3 Standard, at a cost of \$1.15.
- POST, PUT, DELETE, COPY, LIST requests: 100,000 requests per month, costing \$0.50.
- GET and SELECT requests: 100,000 requests per month, costing \$0.04.
- GET requests for the defined 50GB of storage: \$0.135.

Thus, the total estimated monthly cost for S3 was \$1.82. Combining all AWS services, the estimated total monthly cost of the infrastructure, including the EC2 instance hosting the dashboard application, was \$60.05.

During the final stages of development, the actual costs for October were lower than the estimates:

- AWS Glue: The company consumed \$811.72 for 93 jobs, averaging \$8.728 per job. Since the project's tasks took about 3 minutes to execute (compared to the company's jobs, which took over an hour), the actual cost was lower than the calculated average.
- AWS Lambda: The company's 12 Lambda functions incurred a total monthly charge of \$0.29 in October, averaging \$0.024 per function. Two of these functions were specific to the project.
- Amazon S3: The company's storage costs were \$43.625 per bucket, reflecting the significantly larger volume of data (in the gigabytes range) stored compared to the project.

2.4.3 Azure

In the cloud infrastructure designed within the Microsoft Azure environment, as outlined in previous sections, the costs associated with each service were evaluated using the Azure cost calculator [\[45\]](#) for simulations.

The first service considered was Azure Storage Blobs, a highly scalable object storage solution designed to handle the growing demands of data storage. It offers a secure and cost-effective location for storing a wide variety of unstructured data, such as images, videos, documents, and backups, with high availability and durability. Pricing is pay-as-you-go and depends on the type of storage and the amount of space utilized. Based on configurations in the Azure calculator, the following parameters were used:

- Total capacity: 50 GB. Since the reports generated are less than 1 MB each and only a few dozen are created daily, this space is sufficient to store all necessary data.
- Data retrieval: 100 GB.
- Monthly operations: Up to 100,000 of each type (write, read, iterative read, and iterative write).
- Access tier: Cool, used for infrequently accessed data, aligning with the project's needs of several dozen daily accesses.

As a result, the monthly cost for Azure Storage Blobs was estimated at \$3.93.

Next, Azure Data Factory was analyzed. This service acts as an orchestration platform to facilitate data integration, transformation, and movement across heterogeneous and distributed environments. It is fundamental for modern data analysis, offering flexibility and scalability to automate data flows and build ETL pipelines. Using the Azure calculator, the monthly cost was estimated at \$131.91, based on the following parameters:

- Service type: Data Pipeline.
- Integration Runtime: No resources allocated.
- Standard cluster: 1 instance of 8 vCores of general usage and 8 memory-optimized vCores, used for up to 2 hours daily.
- Monthly operations: Up to 50,000 operations of each type (read, write, and monitoring).

Lastly, Azure Data Explorer (ADX) was assessed. ADX is a data analysis platform optimized for handling large volumes of real-time or stored data, enabling complex queries and advanced analytics. Its distributed architecture and efficient query language make it a robust option for Big Data and IoT scenarios. ADX integrates seamlessly with other Azure solutions and provides horizontal scalability, making it suitable for intensive scientific data processing. The monthly cost was estimated at \$95.90, based on the following criteria:

- Environment type: Development and testing.
- Data ingestion: 1 GB per day.
- Cache retention: Hot cache retention for 7 days, with a total data retention of 30 days.
- Engine type: One instance of E2ads v5, running 24 hours a day.
- Monthly operations: 22,500 read and write operations.

For the complete infrastructure set up within the Microsoft environment, the total monthly cost was estimated at \$231.74. During the project's development phase, approximately R\$800.00 was spent in October, distributed as follows:

- R\$ 511,28 for Azure Data Explorer.
- R\$ 291,52 for Azure Data Factory.
- R\$ 1,45 for Azure Storage Blobs.

Overall, the project costs remained within the expected range as estimated in the Azure environment, although they were considered high by the company.

2.5 Analysis of the Proposed Solution (SWOT)

The SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats) can be a useful tool for evaluating cost monitoring and security strategy in a multicloud environment involving AWS and Azure. Therefore, this analysis was developed for the proposed architecture:

2.5.1 Strengths:

- **Integration with Native Services:** The architecture leverages the native services of each cloud provider, such as AWS Glue and Azure Data Factory, for data processing and storage, enhancing efficiency and performance.
- **Custom Monitoring:** By utilizing Grafana alongside a proprietary architecture, custom dashboards can be created with tailored metrics and visualizations, offering a unified and detailed view of relevant information for the company.
- **Versatility of Storage:** By employing services such as S3 (AWS) and Blob Container (Azure), the structure offers flexibility in data management, ensuring scalability and cost optimization.
- **Multidimensional Approach:** The architecture combines financial management and data security, allowing for effective cost control and proactive monitoring against potential threats in a multicloud environment.
- **Approach for Different User Profiles:** Custom dashboards are tailored for users with varying levels of expertise, featuring detailed descriptions and self-explanatory titles that facilitate immediate understanding based on user need.

2.5.2 Weaknesses:

- **Complexity:** The architecture is complex, involving multiple services and processing stages, increases operational demands and requires advanced technical skills for set up and maintenance.
- **Dependence on Third Parties:** The integration of AWS and Azure services with Grafana may lead to compatibility challenges, additional costs, as well as making the dashboard dependent on templates and services from other companies.
- **Dependence on Configurations and Continuous Activity of Agents:** Systems like Wazuh and Zabbix rely on agents that must be continuously configured and active to

collect and transmit metrics, which may introduce maintenance and operational challenges.

- **Limitations in Detailed Cost Visualization:** Without a tagging system in AWS, achieving a detailed and accurate view of costs by project is challenging, complicating financial analysis and control at a project level..

2.5.3 Opportunities:

- **Cost Optimization:** Centralizing cost data analysis from various sources can reveal opportunities to optimize expenditure across both clouds, helping to reduce overall costs.
- **Improvements in Security:** Monitoring security in multicloud environments can uncover vulnerabilities or threats in one cloud that may not be apparent in others, enabling timely and effective corrective actions..
- **Continuous Innovation:** The multicloud nature of the architecture offers ongoing opportunities to explore new resources and services from different providers, facilitating the adoption of emerging technologies and best practices.
- **Scalability to New Environments:** The architecture is scalable and can be expanded to include additional AWS and Azure accounts, or replicated to support other cloud environments.
- **Adaptation for New Metrics:** The system's flexibility enables the easy addition, removal, and monitoring of new metrics, allowing for continuous improvement and customization of the monitoring process.

2.5.4 Threats:

- **Compliance Issues:** Managing compliance in multicloud environments can be challenging due to differing policies and data security regulations from each provider, which may pose compliance risks.
- **Rising Costs:** The complexity of the architecture and the use of third-party services may lead to unexpected costs, especially if expenditures are not closely monitored.
- **Potential Change in Grafana's Model:** While there is no indication that Grafana's business model will change, using an open-source tool that is currently free always

carries the risk of transitioning to a paid version, which could impact accessibility and increase costs for the project.

3. Results and Discussion

At the start of the project, delays occurred in providing credentials for access to the AWS and Azure environments in the PinPag account due to contractual and legal issues. As a result, by the time of the intermediate delivery, a homologation version was delivered in the Insuper environment. Once the issue was resolved, the project proceeded in the PinPag environment as initially planned, leading to the development of the dashboard in full accordance with the guidelines, alignments, and points discussed with the company throughout the project.

3.1 AWS

On the AWS platform, cost-related data was generated in Parquet format and stored appropriately in an Amazon S3 bucket. Crawlers were set up to analyze the data stored in S3, with the goal of identifying formats and inferring the schema structures of this data. The resulting metadata was then stored in a database integrated with the AWS Glue environment. A job was created in Glue to run a series of queries that generate additional tables related to the KPIs, which were stored in a separate segment of the bucket. Additionally, AWS Glue automatically generates metadata related to the processed data, which allows Amazon Athena to execute queries on this data. Athena serves as a connector for the subsequent transmission of information to Grafana. The architecture also includes a backup policy, ensuring the availability of tool data, as well as a deletion policy to remove obsolete data. Section [2.3.1](#) provides detailed information on these results.

3.2 Azure

On the Azure platform, relevant cost data was generated in CSV format and placed into a Blob Container. Within the Data Factory, two pipelines were created, each with its respective trigger. These pipelines were configured to receive data from the container and perform specific operations necessary for KPI construction. Triggers were implemented to initiate the pipelines whenever a new data set is generated and stored. A cluster was then built in the Data Explorer

to ingest the processed data and execute queries, which were visualized in Grafana. The architecture also includes a backup policy and a deletion policy to ensure data availability while reducing storage for obsolete data. Section [2.3.2](#) details these results.

3.3 Zabbix, Wazuh and Grafana

Integration with Grafana was successfully implemented on both the AWS and Azure platforms. It was observed that Grafana uses Athena to execute queries directly on the bucket containing the already processed data. Additionally, further information about the AWS environment was accessed via CloudWatch, while Azure uses the Data Explorer tool to run queries using the Kusto Query Language (KQL). Data collection for Zabbix and Wazuh was also successful, and their visual representations appeared as expected in the dashboard. All results can be found in sections [2.3.3](#), [2.3.4](#) and [2.2.5](#) of this report. Furthermore, images of all dashboard screens are available in Section [5](#) of the appendix.

3.4 Evaluation

The completion of the project was marked by presenting the final product to stakeholders, including the main users who would benefit from the tool. During this phase, the development team conducted a detailed demonstration, followed by the distribution of access credentials to PinPag users. These credentials allowed users to access the dashboard and test the tool in their daily work environment during a one-week trial period.

At the end of this period, users provided feedback on their experiences, highlighting several key technical aspects for the effective representation of data. Among the positive feedback points were:

- **Dashboard Layout and Organization:** The layout and organization of the dashboards were praised for providing a clear and structured view of financial information, which simplified the interpretation and analysis of costs associated with PinPag accounts in AWS and Azure. This includes cost breakdowns, cost variations, and opportunities for optimization.
- **Resource Monitoring Dashboards:** The resource monitoring dashboards were appreciated for offering a real-time view of performance, enabling the technical team to monitor, analyze, and optimize computing resources in cloud accounts, while also maintaining a historical data record for future analyses.

However, users also provided suggestions for improvement. They indicated a need for customized alerts for some of the metrics monitored by Grafana and suggested including metrics related to disk usage. Overall, the feedback indicated that user expectations were met, and the platform will now be used by the company to monitor costs and the security of its multicloud environment — this being the primary objective of the project. The suggested improvements aim to enhance the dashboard without compromising the fulfillment of the established requirements. These suggestions focus on improving the user experience and adding additional functionalities, contributing to more efficient monitoring and management of the company's multicloud resources.

4. Conclusion and Outlook

Throughout the development of the project, several opportunities for enhancing and improving the final product were identified. These considerations aim not only to expand the functionality of the dashboard but also to strengthen aspects of automation, scalability, and security. Below are some key points that can be explored in future iterations:

4.1 Authentication System in Conjunction with VPN

Given the importance of security, adding an additional authentication system during login can serve as a strong security measure, preventing potential leaks. In addition to the existing VPN, exploring and implementing multifactor authentication (MFA) methods or Single Sign-On (SSO) solutions can further enhance protection against unauthorized access. This additional layer of security would be especially important, considering the sensitivity of the information handled in the dashboard.

4.2 Optimization of Azure Architecture

Currently, the Azure architecture uses Data Explorer for both the ingestion of processed data and as a bridge for sending data to Grafana for visualization. This approach differs from AWS Athena, where charges are based on the number of queries made by the graphical tool. In contrast, Data Explorer operates differently. As previously mentioned, a cluster was established to manage both query and storage services, running continuously 24 hours a day. This continuous operation incurs costs, including the operational costs of the cluster, such as reading

and writing to the database. A similar scenario is observed in Data Factory, where costs are based on the number of processing cores used per hour. To mitigate these expenses, considering the adoption of Azure Synapse Analytics could be beneficial, as it offers similar functionality to AWS Athena in terms of both pricing and features. For Data Factory, using Azure Functions for data processing might be another viable option. However, this would require the creation of a new Grafana connector for Azure, as the tool currently only supports Data Explorer and Azure DevOps services.

4.3 Infrastructure Automation via Terraform

Integrating Terraform for infrastructure automation could be a valuable addition to the project. Implementing Infrastructure as Code (IaC) using Terraform not only provides efficient standardization but also ensures optimized scalability. Additionally, incorporating a robust versioning system would enable precise control over changes to the infrastructure, facilitating both updates and rollbacks. The implementation of an automated process would also significantly simplify the replication of this setup for other cloud infrastructures, streamlining and accelerating the process.

4.4 Vulnerability Analysis Reports

Performing a vulnerability analysis on the final product, as well as across all cloud infrastructures, after adding new instances and services, is crucial for maintaining a secure and controlled environment for the company. This proactive step helps to reduce the potential for security failures and breaches. Tools such as OWASP ZAP or Greenbone can be integrated to conduct comprehensive security assessments. By using these tools, systematic scans and vulnerability analyses can be performed, resulting in detailed reports that identify potential security gaps early on. This enables the implementation of corrective measures, as recommended in these reports.

In summary, the considerations and improvements outlined above offer a promising path for the ongoing enhancement of the project and its application within the company's multicloud environment. Each point provides tangible opportunities to strengthen security, scalability, automation, and the overall efficiency of the dashboard. By exploring these future perspectives, it is expected that the functional and security expectations of the system will not

only be met but exceeded, fostering a robust and reliable environment for managing multicloud resources.

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5. Appendix A

- **Images of the AWS cost and usage dashboard:**

- **Images of the Azure cost and usage dashboard:**

- **Images of the Zabbix hardware monitoring dashboard:**

- **Images of the Wazuh vulnerability monitoring dashboard:**

